

**AN ANALYSIS OF THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN
SCHOOL MANAGERS'S INDUCTION CAPACITY AND
THE IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AT PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS
IN NYERI COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

Some of the primary school managers in Kenya lack induction capacity to implement the human resource development policy. Induction of new teachers is a key aspect of the human resource development policy. The purpose of this study was to analyze the association between school manager's induction capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools in Nyeri County. The behavioral theory of management and the policy formulation and implementation theories were used to guide this study. The survey and in-depth interviews methods were used to collect quantitative and qualitative data respectively. The concurrent triangulation design was applied during data collection and analysis of both the qualitative and quantitative data. The target population included head teachers, teachers, chairpersons of the boards of management in public primary schools and the sub county TSC human resource officers. The independent variable was school manager's induction capacity while the dependent variable was the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools. The target population of the study consisted of four hundred (400) headteachers, one thousand six hundred (1600) teachers, four hundred (400) chairpersons of public primary schools board of management and eight (8) sub county TSC human resource officers. Stratified Random Sampling was applied to select a sample size of fifty (50) head teachers, one hundred and sixty (160) teachers and fifty (50) board of management chairpersons in public primary schools. Eight (8) Sub County TSC Human Resource Officers were purposively selected. The questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from

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head teachers and teachers in the selected public primary schools. Additionally, interview schedules were used to collect qualitative data from chairpersons of the schools' board of management and from the sub county TSC human resource officers. Validity was enhanced by piloting of instruments prior to collecting the final data. To enhance credibility, adjustments of the tools were done according to the opinion obtained from respondents of the piloting and the advice provided by supervisors. Interactive questioning was used to enhance dependability. Qualitative data was analyzed thematically. The Chi square was applied for analysis of inferential statistics. This was done with the help of SPSS program version 24. Qualitative data was compared with quantitative data at the final analysis. The reporting of the quantitative data included percentages, tables and charts while qualitative data was by the Chi square values, inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that school managers have positive attitude towards conducting induction in their respective schools and that there exist a policy on induction. However, the school managers were found to have little time to conduct induction owing to other responsibilities assigned. The researcher recommended that headteachers of public primary schools should be properly trained on the induction process to enhance induction of teachers in their schools. Additionally, the school managers should have a reduced workload and adequate finances to enable them to carry out the teacher's induction role effectively.

Keywords: induction, headteachers, human resource development policy, implementation

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Anglo American researchers give four dimensions that define education pegged on interpersonal, moral, administrative and instructional dimensions (Lawler, 2003). The latest literature of education leadership can be divided into four based on areas of perspective pedagogy that focus on instructional leadership as involvement of skills that improves teaching, action research and development of curriculum. Professional norms that required principals to be involved more actively leading programmes of school instructions and concentrating staff attention on learner's outcome are prevalent (Swanson, 2001).

While managers in western nations were observed to be involving in some areas of instructional leadership (Swanson, 2001), they have been noted to center on instructional roles as compared to school managers in developing nations and have been assumed to be as a result of environmental diversity at schools. In comparison, principals in South East Asia were found to engage in a great way to instructional leadership. Principals in Singapore were also required to give instructional leadership to human resource. Further, Chinese headteachers are found to have perfect instructions as vital aspects towards school prestige and student success. It was also

observed that principals from Thailand greatly exercise instructional leadership which is slightly different from Hong Kong where school managers are moderate in engaging instructional leadership and therefore achieve greater heights of indirect engagement (Guskey, 2000).

In Africa, Ghana is one of the nations recognized for its effective curriculum implementation processes, for its headteachers see their duties as being efforts in assisting staffs to employ modern instructional means and implement curricula which is lately introduced. However, instructional leadership roles are relatively low in schools that are in the third world countries whereby headteachers are probably to involve a stance of administration and management favoritism. Effective instruction is directly involved to learners' achievement so as the greater effectiveness levels, then the higher students' performance levels. In Kuwait for example, the curriculum is not directly associated to the work of the headteacher and research studies carried out in New Guinea and also in Thailand shows that headteachers in these nations are ranked lower on the basis terms of instructional; leadership inventories as opposed to their counterparts in western nations (Lahui-Ako, 2001).

The ministry of education is responsible for educational policy formulation in Kenya. However, the policy implementation is left to county directors and school managers at regional level. Mathias & Jackson, (2004) argued that human resource development policy is quite important for collective bargaining by teachers. The school management should ensure that teachers are properly motivated especially in their working conditions and environs.

The human resource development policy further outlines measures and strategies for ensuring that human resource development and capacity building in the public service is guided by Articles 10, 27, 54, 55, 56, 232 and Chapter six of the Kenya Constitution (Republic of Kenya, 2004).

2. Statement of the Problem

Implementation of induction at the public primary schools in Kenya is shallow due to lack of school management capacity and diverse policy interpretation by school managers. School managers have been reported to lack important induction skills consequently hindering the implementation of human resource policy.

Inducting new teachers is a key role of school managers. However, lack of prior management training often lead to poor induction of teachers thus hindering the implementation of the human resource policy. In regard to this challenge of management capacity, the researcher developed interest to analyze the association between school manager's induction capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy at public primary schools in Nyeri County.

2.1 Research Objective

To establish the association between school manager's induction capacity and the implementation of human resource development policy in public primary schools.

2.2 Research Hypothesis

H01-There is no association between school manager's induction capacity and the implementation of the human resource development policy in public primary schools.

2.3 Significance of the Study

The education sector may adopt various recommendations from this study to improve on policy formulation and implementation in regard to induction process in public primary schools.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Teachers as Human Resource Personnel

Heneman et al (2005), defines human resource as a group of individuals giving rise to workforce in an economy, business sector or an organization. Additionally, human capital is also used to refer human resource but contains a narrow meaning. Human capital is the knowledge an individual can contribute to an organization. In schools, there are various human resources that include school managers, teaching staffs and non-teaching staffs who facilitate school goals, mission and vision. Teachers are human resource in a school setting that enables acquires skills, competencies and knowledge.

3.2 Human Resource Development Policy Implementation in Schools

According to Armstrong (2001), human policies are necessary guidelines in an institution that it intends to use in order to effectively manage its people. Therefore, human resource policy implementation is decisions making and taking actions on daily problems in an institution that involves objective identification and examining alternative means to solve the problems (McConnell, 2005). Human resource management was naming that replaced personnel management in previous days.

3.3 Teachers Induction and the Implementation of the Human Resource Development Policy

Alvenfors (2010) stated that induction is a process that many companies use in order to welcome their novice employees in an organization for effective preparation in their new duties. Therefore, induction involves practical skills and theoretical development required by new employees including interaction need among the novice employees. Further, induction involves safety training to contractors before the beginning of their new jobs. Thus, it aims at the particular safety matters in an organization but often involves company information that is delivered to workers.

Browning (2004) stipulates that the benefit of induction process is mainly for bringing new staff into an institution. The researcher also reveals that induction enables effective introduction of employees into the working environment and establish a well set up the working system into an organization. Nevertheless, the induction process covers the employees and employers rights, term and conditions of the work contract. Induction must also prioritize all compliance and legal requirements required for working at an organization and importantly, consider safety and health matters to novice employees. Induction in an organization is also gaining of knowledge management and aims to assist new employees so as to become useful, effective integration to other working team instead "thrown in to the deep end" without knowledge of job performance and how they will fit into the company.

Matiku (2003) stated that induction training is among of various types of orientation or training, promotional training, job training, corrective training and refreshment training which is introduced to a novice worker into new work, introduced to his new co-employees and new situation. The novice worker is introduced to the working rues, privileges, organization activities, working conditions, daily operations of the organization, customer service, the other particular and the community involved to attain the mission of the organization. Armstrong (2008) points out that induction is a process of welcoming retrieving employees when they initially join the organization and giving the essential data they require to happily and settle to start the job.

4. Research Methodology and Design

4.1 Research Methodology

The study adapted the survey method in collecting quantitative data while interviews were used in collecting qualitative data. According to Kerlinger (1973), survey research is a study on large and small populations which involves selecting samples from the target population in order to find out interrelations.

4.2 Research Design

This study adapted the concurrent triangulation design. A concurrent design allows analysis, interpretation and comparison of both qualitative and quantitative data. This design is usually used when a direct comparison or contrast is needed in Quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings (Creswell, Plano Clark et al, 2003).

5. Research Findings

5.1 Association between School Manager's Induction Capacity and the Implementation of the Human Resource Development Policy

Table 1 indicates that school managers have a positive attitude towards conducting teachers' mentorship in their respective schools. This was supported by 23(51%) of headteachers agreeing, 17(38%) strongly agreeing while none of school headteacher

strongly disagreed. Further, teachers responded that school managers had positive attitude towards conducting teacher's mentorship. A large number of teachers, 72(48%) agreed, 57(38%) strongly agreed, while only 1(1%) strongly disagreed. The findings of this study aligns with ACAS (2015) that stated that, new worker should be inducted through use of well-established recruitment, the best use of company resource to effectively conduct induction process and most importantly to provide long term benefits to workers in an organization. Through these necessities, the report stated that the administration should remain positive for effective preparation of new workers arrival and their effective integration to school's daily operations. These findings are similar to Lussier (2000) who stated that benefits accrued from induction processes include assisting personnel to perform in standard points, acquiring the right perception of what is required from them, good cooperation with other employees and reduction of anxiety emanating from their duties.

Table 1: Views by Respondents on School Manager's Induction Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy

Summary of Test Items	Headteachers					Teachers				
	SA	A	N	D	SD	SA	A	N	D	SD
	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F	F
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
1. School managers' have positive attitude towards teachers' mentorship	17	23	3	2	0	51	12	13	4	1
	38	51	7	4	0	38	48	9	3	1
2. There is effective coaching activities to conduct induction at schools	14	10	11	5	5	48	67	22	7	4
	31	22	24	11	11	32	45	15	5	3
3. Views on availability of time to conduct successful induction in my school	4	9	9	16	7	1	4	13	60	69
	9	20	20	35	16	1	3	9	40	46
4. There is enough resources for successful induction and support to teachers	3	11	5	16	10	21	1	21	63	63
	7	24	11	35	22	14	1	14	42	42
5. Headteachers are trained on teachers' orientation to implement human resource development policy	1	7	19	19	11	13	1	28	61	60
	2	15	15	42	24	9	1	19	41	40

A fair number of the headteachers revealed that there was effective coaching activities where 14(31%), strongly agreed, 10(22%) agreed and 11(24%) were neutral while the least number of 5(11%) strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. Similarly, teachers indicated that there is effective coaching to conduct induction in schools where 48(32%) strongly agreed, 67(45%) agreed while 7(5%) disagreed and a further 4(3%) strongly disagreed. On this particular question 22(15%) of the teachers chose to remain neutral. These findings correspond with those of Gless (2001) who stated that effective and strong induction process enables increased retention of new teachers. The researcher further stated that well inducted teachers are twice likely to stay in the profession of teaching compared to those who are never involved. Positive and well established induction programs had been noted to be effective for teachers since they

have fewer indiscipline problems compared to those teachers who do not undergo induction process.

Matiku (2003) stated that induction training is among of various types of orientation or training, promotional training, job training, corrective training and refreshment training which is introduced to a novice worker into new work, introduced to his new co-employees and new situation. The novice worker is introduced to the working rues, privileges, organization activities, working conditions, daily operations of the organization, customer service, the other particular and the community involved to attain the mission of the organization.

When asked whether there was enough time to conduct successful induction, the responses were as follows. A considerable number 16 (35%) of the headteachers disagreed and a further 7(16%) strongly disagreed, 9(20%) were neutral and only 4(9%) agreed. There were similar views from teachers on the same question. Majority of the teachers 69(46%) strongly disagreed that there was enough time to conduct induction and 60(40%) strongly agreed, 13(9%) were neutral on the matter while 1(1%) strongly disagreed and a further 4(3%) agreed.

These findings affirm a study by Simatwa (2010), who stated that induction can be lengthy and difficult process and encouraged that new teachers need assistance for both curriculum and extra curriculum activities. Another study by Idoshi (2003) also found out that induction for newly qualified educators in Kenya is informal and haphazard. The researcher continues to state that teachers rarely benefit from induction processes in Kenya. Induction activities require to be funded according to newly recruited educators' unique needs.

The researcher also sought the views of the respondents on the availability of enough resources for successful induction and support of teachers. Only 3(7%) of the headteachers strongly agreed, 11(24%) agreed and 5(11%) remained neutral. Still on the headteachers a fair number 16(35%) disagreed and 10(22%) strongly disagreed. The teachers who responded echoed the same sentiments with the largest number 63(42%) disagreeing and a similar number 63(42%) strongly disagreeing. Those who remained neutral were 21(14%) a similar number 21(14%) strongly agreed while only 1(1%) agreed.

On the question of whether headteachers are trained on teachers orientation to implement human resource policy, only 1(2%) strongly agreed while 7(15%) agreed, a similar number 7(15%) remained neutral while the highest number 19(42%) disagreed and 11(24%) disagreed. The teachers who responded on the same shared similar views, with 60(40%) strongly disagreeing and the largest number 61(41%) disagreeing. However 13(9%) maintained a neutral perspective while 13(9%) strongly agreed. Only 1(1%) of the teachers agreed. These findings align to that of Ajowi (2011) who found out that challenges encountered during induction activities in schools as stated by most school heads includes; work overload, financial constraints, inadequate time to offer comprehensive induction processes, lack of policies that are printed regarding

induction processes in schools and inadequate knowledge by mentors regarding induction processes.

Table 2 reveals the analysis of Chi Tests for Association between School Manager's Induction Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy.

Table 2: Association between School Manager's Induction Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy

		There is enough finances for successful induction and support to teachers											
		Headteachers						Teachers					
		SA	A	N	D	SD	Total	SA	A	N	D	SD	Total
There is ample time to conduct successful induction in my school	Strongly Agree	1	1	1	0	1	4	25	28	7	0	60	60
	Agree	1	4	1	2	1	9	27	30	10	2	69	69
	Neutral	0	1	1	4	3	9	8	4	2	0	14	14
	Disagree	0	5	0	7	4	16	1	1	0	0	2	2
	Strongly Disagree	1	0	2	3	1	7	2	0	2	0	4	4
Total		3	11	5	16	10	45		63	63	21	2	149

However, the Chi tests are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Chi Tests for Association between School Manager's Induction Capacity and the Implementation of Human Resource Development Policy

	Headteachers			Teachers		
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.842 ^a	16	.396	.140 ^a	12	.604
Likelihood Ratio	.566	16	.158	.419	12	.493
N of Valid Cases	45			149		

* Association is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 ** Association is significant at the 0.00 level (2-tailed).

According to Table 3, data was presented in a matrix. A Chi square was run to establish the association between school managers' induction capacity and implementation of human resource development policy. The test generated Chi square coefficients of $\chi^2 = .842$ and $.140$ with corresponding significant levels of $p = .396$ for headteachers and $p = .604$ for teachers which were both greater than the already determined level of significance of 0.05, that is p-values of 0.396 and 0.604 are greater 0.05. These findings clearly shown that there was no significant statistical association between school managers' induction res and implementation of human resource development policy. The hypothesis H₀₁, which stated that there was no association between school managers' induction capacity and implementation of human resource development policy was therefore accepted.

Further, to establish the association between school manager's induction capacity and implementation of human resource development policy Sub-County Human

Resource Officers (SHRO) and Board of Managers (BOM) members were interviewed. The first question was to establish how induction of teachers is carried out in schools. However, a majority of BOM and SHRO disclosed that in school settings human resource induction is less practised in public primary schools with 60% and 54% respectively stating that the schools they manage are not practising human resource induction. For instance, BOM chairpersons had the common view that *“most public primary schools do not offer induction among their human resource however, we are enacting measures that will lead to effective induction practices in public primary schools”*. Similar remarks were found among SCHR officers whereby six officers remarked that *“most schools rarely practices induction, due to lack of awareness by school managers to conduct induction in public primary schools”*. Most interviewees echoed similar sentiments that most schools do not practice induction and if it exists, it is rarely done and that measures were being enacted that would lead to effective conduction of induction processes in public primary schools. Through these sentiments by Board of Management Chairpersons and Sub County Human Resource Officers, the study reveals that induction is not done in primary schools thus impeding teachers' performances.

5.2 Recommendations

The study found out that, school managers have positive attitude towards conducting induction in their respective schools. This augurs well with the fact that, a new worker should be inducted through use of well-established recruitment process, the best use of company resources to effectively conduct induction process and most importantly to provide long term benefits to workers in an organization. In regard to this necessity, the report stated that the administration should remain positive for effective preparation of new workers arrival and their effective integration into school daily operations. Further, the study established that there was effective policy regarding induction process in the sampled schools. Both head teachers and teachers revealed that schools have established that there is effective policy to conduct induction. This enables induction processes to be done effectively in schools by ensuring guidelines are adhered and new teachers are introduced in their new task successfully. This helped school managers to induct novice teachers in their respective schools that included; introducing them to colleagues, introduction to curriculum used, introduction to learning and teaching materials, introduction to school environment, advising new teachers among others.

The study recommends that public primary schools should put in place measures to ensure effective implementation of the outlined induction processes. Further, it will assist schools to have a rigid guidelines, the materials involved and facilitators required for induction.

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